

A new method for on-line dissolution and determination of trace impurities in high silica material using inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry

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Abstract : A simple and rapid method has been developed for on-line dissolution of high silica material followed by the determination of trace impurities in ICP-AES. High silica material was placed in a mixture of HF and water (1 : 2) inside a polypropylene bottle. After capping the lid, the bottle was kept at room temperature (25 ± 5) °C for 45 min with occasional manual shaking. The resultant solution in HF was tested for metallic trace impurities directly in ICP-AES. The test result of the rapid dissolution technique was checked with those obtained by conventional dissolution of the material in supra pure HF. The results obtained by two different sample dissolution techniques were in very good agreement. Accuracy of the method has been verified by analyzing certified reference high silica materials like quartz, SAB, SARM 49 and high purity silica, BCS-CRM.313/1.

Keywords : High silica materials, acid dissolution, polypropylene bottle, ICP-AES.

Introduction

Quartz or silica sand is the basic raw material used for the manufacture of glass^{1,2}. Transition metal impurities very often present in raw materials, are the most perturbing elements which adversely affect the quality of the product. Special glasses demand high purity quartz and therefore there is an increasing need to develop rapid and accurate method for the analysis of trace impurities present in quartz.

Several techniques such as ICP-AES³⁻⁵, AAS⁶⁻⁹, ion chromatography¹⁰ and spectrophotometry^{11,12} have been used for rapid and accurate determination of elemental impurities in quartz or silica sand. But too long a time is required for complete dissolution of the material before its analysis. The routinely used sample pre-treatment involves complete dissolution of the matrix using HF¹³ and complete evaporation of silica matrix as SiF₄ before trace metals determination. This complete dissolution and subsequent evaporation step is very lengthy and there is a possibility of contamination.

In view of the problems associated with the dissolution of high silica materials, the ultimate approach of

silica matrix dissolution while preventing the introduction of impurities, is by vapor phase decomposition (VPD)¹⁴ instead of conventional HF dissolution. Specially designed teflon vessels¹⁵, teflon blocks¹⁶, PTFE apparatus⁵ and pressure bombs¹⁷ have been routinely used as reaction chambers for the VPD of quartz and silicon powders. A VPD procedure for trace element determination in high purity quartz at 180 °C in a sealed PTFE bomb⁵ has been reported. Measurement and control of temperature and pressure inside such pressurized vessels requires special sensors, the lack of which could result in serious safety problems¹⁸. In most of the reported VPD procedures^{5,17,19} only 1–2 samples can be digested within a time period of 8–12 h. Thus the determination of trace impurities in a large number of high purity quartz samples on a routine basis using VPD is time-consuming. In the present work the decomposition process has been simplified by using a polypropylene bottle for the dissolution of quartz sample in HF at room temperature (25 ± 5) °C. After dissolution of the sample within 45 min, trace impurities present in it have been determined by direct introduction of sample solution in ICP-AES. The aim of the present study was to investigate the efficiency of HF

acid extraction of quartz at room temperature and to compare it with conventional dissolution technique which is routinely used for determination of trace impurities in quartz. The parameters influencing the acid extraction, such as extraction temperature, extraction time and extraction composition were investigated.

Results and discussion

In order to optimize the parameters for HF acid dissolution of quartz powder, a series of experiments were carried out.

Effect of temperature :

Temperature has tremendous effect on the dissolution of high silica material in HF and optimization of temperature is needed. A series of experiments were done taking 0.2 g of quartz powder in a mixture of HF and water (1 : 2) inside polypropylene bottles. After capping the lid of the bottles, the mixtures were kept for 45 min varying temperature from 15 to 40 °C with manual shaking after each 15 min interval. The concentration of trace impurities in acid extracted solutions were determined in ICP-AES. Fig. 1 shows that percent leaching of trace impurities increases with the increase of temperature and remain constant after 25 °C. Therefore, optimum temperature for quantitative leaching of trace impurities present

Fig. 1. Concentration of trace impurities in acid extraction with temperature.

in high silica material in HF acid is (25 ± 5) °C.

Effect of time :

The effect of dissolution time of high silica material in HF is very important for obtaining quantitative extraction of trace impurities present in it. Extraction of trace analytes from quartz powder was carried out as a function of time using a mixture of HF and water (1 : 2) at room temperature. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that a minimum of 45 min is required for quantitative extraction of trace analytes like Al, Ti, Fe, Ca, Mg, Mn, Na and K. On increasing of HF acid concentration further, no reduction in time for quantitative recovery of trace elements was observed. Thus, optimum extraction efficiency for trace elements in a mixture of HF and water (1 : 2) at room temperature was achieved within 45 min.

Fig. 2. Extraction of trace impurities with time.

Table 1. Instrumentation and operating conditions of ICP-AES

RF generator power	2.5 KW
Radio frequency	27.12 MHz
Torch	Demountable quartz torch
Nebulizer	Meinhard concentric type with scott type spray chamber
RF forward power	1.2 KW
Argon gas flow rates :	
Collant	15 L min ⁻¹
Auxillary	1.01 L min ⁻¹
Nebulizer	1.01 L min ⁻¹
Mebulizer pressure	3.4 bar
Sample uptake rate	1 ml min ⁻¹
Optical resolution	0.009 nm

Effect of HF concentration :

Concentration of HF is the most important factor on which extraction efficiency of trace analytes from high silica materials depends. In order to optimize HF acid concentration, a series of experiments were carried out using a mixture of HF and water at the ratios varying from (1 : 4) to (1 : 1). From this study it was found that quantitative extraction of elements like Al, Fe, Ti, Ca, Mg, Na, K and Mn from quartz powder has been achieved using the mixture (1 : 2) of HF and water.

Selection of spectral lines :

The most critical analytical parameter in developing a method for ICP emission is the wavelength. With a sequential scanning system, optimum wavelengths are selected for each element. Wavelength selection depends on the sample matrix and expected concentration range of the elements of interest. To select the best wavelength for the analysis of trace elements present in high silica material, a multi-element standard containing elements having concentration (mg L⁻¹) ranges of Al (1-16), Fe (0.5-8.0), Ti (0.5-8.0), Ca (0.1-1.6), Mg (0.05-0.8), Na (0.1-1.6), K (0.1-1.6), Zr (0.5-8.0), Cr (0.1-1.6) and Mn (0.005-0.08) in 2% nitric acid was prepared. Various emission lines were scanned while aspirating this standard to obtain optimum wavelengths for these analytes. The spectral lines were selected on the basis of minimum spectral line interference and maximum sensitivity. For the present work, wavelengths used in ICP analysis is given in Table 2.

To investigate the extraction efficiency of the present

method, the concentrations of trace impurities in high silica materials using conventional method, as described in the experimental section, were determined. The extraction effect of the present method was compared with the results of the conventional dissolution method. The proposed method was applied to standard reference materials (SRM) in order to estimate accuracy and precision of the concentration of different elements by this method. The analytical results given in Table 3 show good agreement with the certified values which demonstrates that the concentrations of trace impurities with sufficient accuracy can be obtained by this method. The *t*-test was applied to examine whether the results obtained by the present method differed significantly at the 95% confidence level. As the calculated '*t*' values were less than the critical '*t*' value of 2.571 (degree of freedom of 5), it shows that there was no statistically significant differences among the results obtained by the proposed method and the routinely used dissolution method.

Experimental

All reagents, unless specified otherwise, were of analytical reagent grade. De-ionized water (18 mega ohm resistivity) prepared from the Millipore milli-Q water purification system, USA, was used throughout.

Hydrofluoric acid, HF (40%) Ultra Pure, Merck.

Standard stock (1000 mg L⁻¹) solutions of Al, Fe, Ti, Ca, Mg, Na, K and Mn, Merck, Germany, for preparation of multi-elemental calibration standard.

All standard solutions were kept in polypropylene bottles.

Table 2. Wavelengths of elements measured by ICP-AES

Element	Wavelength (nm)	Concentration range (mg L ⁻¹)	Detection limit (µg L ⁻¹)	Concentration coefficient
Al (I)	308.215	1-16.0	45.94	0.9999
Fe (II)	259.940	0.5-8.0	6.41	0.9999
Ti (II)	334.941	0.5-8.0	6.44	1.0000
Ca (II)	393.366	0.1-1.6	0.17	0.9998
Mg (II)	279.553	0.05-0.8	0.19	0.9996
Na (I)	589.592	0.1-1.6	8.69	0.9998
K (I)	766.490	0.1-1.6	7.70	0.9997
Zr (II)	343.823	0.5-8.0	2.03	0.9998
Cr (II)	205.552	0.1-1.6	1.31	0.9995
Mn (II)	257.610	0.005-0.08	0.18	0.9997

I : atomic lines; II : ionic lines.

Table 3. Accuracy check results of ICP-AES with standard reference materials

High purity silica, BCS CRM 313/1						
Element (oxide)	Certified value (wt%)	Analytical results ^a (wt%)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	S _c	t _{Calcd.}
Al ₂ O ₃	0.036	0.037 ± 0.0009	102.77	2.50	±0.0003	2.48
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.012	0.0119 ± 0.0002	99.17	1.67	±0.0002	1.12
TiO ₂	0.017	0.018 ± 0.00	105.88	0.00	±0.00	0.00
CaO	0.006	0.0059 ± 0.0002	98.33	3.33	±0.00004	1.12
MgO	0.0013	0.0012 ± 0.00	92.31	0.00	±0.00	0.00
Na ₂ O	0.003	0.0029 ± 0.0001	96.67	3.33	±0.00004	2.23
K ₂ O	0.005	0.0049 ± 0.0001	98.00	2.00	±0.0002	2.23
MnO	0.00013	0.00014 ± 0.00	107.69	0.00	±0.00	0.00
Quartz, SABS SARM 49						
Element (oxide)	Certified value (wt%)	Analytical results ^a (wt%)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	S _c	t _{Calcd.}
Al ₂ O ₃	0.05	0.048 ± 0.002	96.00	4.00	±0.0004	2.23
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.05	0.051 ± 0.001	102.00	2.00	±0.0003	2.23
TiO ₂	0.01	0.0095 ± 0.0003	95.00	3.00	±0.0001	3.72
CaO	0.01	0.0094 ± 0.00	94.00	0.00	±0.00	0.00
MgO	0.05	0.049 ± 0.0009	98.00	1.80	±0.0004	2.48
Na ₂ O	0.05	0.052 ± 0.00	104.00	0.00	±0.00	0.00
K ₂ O	0.01	0.009 ± 0.00	90.00	0.00	±0.00	0.00
MnO	0.01	0.009 ± 0.00	90.00	0.00	±0.00	0.00

S_c : Standard error, ^amean of five determinations ± sd, ^bt-test at 95% confidence level.

Instrumentation :

Elemental analysis were performed by ICP-AES, model Spectroflame Modula FTM 08, sequential inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (Spectro, Germany). HF resistant sample introduction system was used. The instrumentation and operating conditions are summarized in Table 1.

Sample solution preparation :

Present method :

Approximately 0.2 g of high silica containing sample (-200 mesh and oven dried at 105 °C) was weighed and taken in a 50 ml polypropylene bottle. A mixture of 5 ml HF and 10 ml water was added to the sample and after capping the lid, the bottle was kept for dissolution of the sample at room temperature (25 ± 5) °C for 45 min with manual shaking after each 15 min interval. The solution was introduced into ICP-AES for trace metal determination.

Conventional method :

Approximately 0.5 g of high silica sample (-200 mesh

and oven dried 105 °C) was weighed and taken in a platinum basin. A mixture of HF (5 ml) and HNO₃ (2 ml) was added to the basin and the sample was digested on a sand bath for evaporation of silica as SiF₄. The process was repeated till complete dissolution of the sample. In order to remove excess HF, 2 ml of HNO₃ was added and evaporated near dryness. This step was repeated and residue was dissolved in 2% (v/v) HNO₃ and transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask. A blank solution was prepared using the same procedure.

Conclusion :

The proposed method for dissolution of high silica material provides a simple and fast approach for ICP-AES determination of trace impurities present in it. The advantages are :

- use of simple and inexpensive polypropylene bottle instead of costly platinum-ware,
- drastic reduction in sample pre-treatment time (45 min) compared to conventional dissolution technique (7-8 h),

- (c) complete elimination of expensive fume chamber,
- (d) use of very low volume of HF for extraction lowers process blank and
- (e) contamination risk is minimized since the complete sample preparation is carried out in closed conditions.

Most of all, this simple, fast and inexpensive method do not compromise the quality of analytical results.

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